

Supplementary Table 2. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of viable seeds of *J. mollissima* determined by the tetrazolium test.

	F	p-value
Lot	3.31	0.020 **
Temperature	19.39	2.47 ⁻⁰⁶ **
Cut	44.91	4.66 ⁻¹² **
Stain	179.42	2.2 ⁻¹⁶ **
Temperature x Cut	1.40	0.236
Temperature x Stain	8.93	0.001 **
Cut x Stain	91.43	2.2 ⁻¹⁶ **
Temperature x Cut x Stain	3.80	0.052

** significant at 5% significance level.